

Constructed wetlands for wastewater treatment including those used for fast-growing timber

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ABSTRACT

Wastewater volume growth is a challenge for most of developing countries and there are several approaches to resolve the problem. But one of the most efficient wastewater treatment method is constructed wetland. This technology clones the processes in a natural ecosystem. The constructed wetland serves habitats for the wild fauna and its substrate takes in similar microbial communities as a natural wetland does. The constructed wetlands are efficient in treating a large scale of xenobiotics such as pesticides or drugs because of a longer water cycle in the basin. By the way this technology is cheaper than conventional analogues such as aeration tanks. The constructed wetland forms a semi-natural microbial environment that contributes self-purification processes in a recipient waterbody. The treated water issued from the constructed wetland can go directly to a river or can be reused in forestry irrigation. Such the systems constructed wetland-fast growing timber plantation have been experienced. This kind of wastewater recycling is likely for the ASEAN countries for climate and economical reasons.

Keywords: Wetland, wastewater

INTRODUCTION

Wastewater volume growth is a challenge for many countries and there are several approaches to resolve this problem. However, one of the most efficient wastewater treatment methods adopted is the constructed wetland. This constructed technology approach clones the processes in a natural ecosystem. The constructed wetland serves as a habitat for wild fauna where its substrate takes in similar microbial communities as a natural wetland does. The constructed wetland consists of amicrophyte community and an artificial substrate that represents in most cases soil, sand, gravel or larger stones. The microphytes that are usually introduced into constructed wetlands are in most cases common reeds, cattails, bulrush and canna lilies.

What is a constructed (treatment) wetland?

Constructed wetland refers to an artificial aquatic ecosystem and in its treatment process does not use the same principals as treatment plants that apply activated sludge. Constructed wetlands differ from other biological treatment systems in that they have longer hydraulic cycles which allow for better water contact and macrobiotic communities (Figure. 1).

Figure 1. Artificial aquatic ecosystem of wetlands

One of the most effective constructed wetlands is one with a horizontal flow of water through a gravel load that is no more than 1.5 m deep with moisture-loving plants placed in it. These include, for example, representatives of the genera Phragmites, Scirpus and Typha. The main way in which constructed wetlands differ from other landscape cleaning systems (lagoons, after-treatment ponds, bioplato, irrigation fields) is the ability to: firstly, build on or add some technical elements (aerators, pumps) whilst maintaining the overall flow of the process as would occur in a natural landscape ecosystem; and secondly, maintain a high water residence time (more than 7-8 days). The technical components of the system enhance the recycling of the flow (Shchegolkova, 2018).

The constructed wetlands for wastewater treatment require a specific range of processes that synergistically clear/clean the sewage. These processes can be classified by:

Biological,

- Microbiological degradation through catabolism and anabolism
- Protozoic predation and digestion
- Plant uptake and storage

Physical,

- Filtration
- Settlement and Chemical,
- Adsorption (ionic and covalent)
- Oxidation
- Reduction
- UV degradation

The assemblage of microorganisms permits efficient nitrification and denitrification in the wastewater. If aeration zones are provided for in the wetland construction, the denitrification process is enhanced and produces better conditions. Effective denitrification is the key process of purification and helps to reduce the quantity of sludge.

Figure 2. Type of microorganisms

The constructed wetlands are efficient in treating a large range of xenobiotics such as pesticides or drugs/medications because of a longer water cycle in the basin. Furthermore, this technology is inexpensive over conventional analogues such as aeration tanks.

The constructed wetland forms a semi-natural microbial environment that features self-purification processes in a recipient waterbody. The treated water issued (effluent) from the constructed wetland should go into a river or be reused in forestry irrigation. The use of this recycled water from the 'constructed wetland' can lead to fast-growing timber plantations as has been experienced previously. The use of this kind of wastewater recycling is likely to become the norm for the ASEAN countries for climate and economic reasons.

Figure 3. Self-purification processes in constructed wetlands

How to construct a wetland?

Different treatment plant designs have various advantages and disadvantages. The free surface constructed wetland is the cheapest but less efficient as compared to others. The hybrid type (combination of the two subsurface CWs) is more efficient.

Surface flow Constructed Wetland is also known as free water surface CW

This is characterized by continuous flow and mainly used for the tertiary treatment of municipal wastewater, storm water runoff, mine drainage and agricultural runoff.

Sub-surface flow Constructed Wetland is also known as Reed Bed Treatment System Intermittent Flow

This type of a constructed wetland is effective for the removal of ammonia to reduce (BOD5) from domestic wastewaters and is the best for wastewaters with relatively low solids concentrations which require relatively uniform flow conditions. These kinds of treatment plants are relatively expensive to construct and more difficult to regulate. The sub-surface flow constructed

wetland generally incurs higher maintenance and repair costs. Furthermore face clogging problems are common.

How efficient are the constructed wetlands?

The removal efficiency of a constructed wetland depends on several factors and these are: location; climate (weather type); type of wastewater or runoff input; wetland design; disturbance; and daily or seasonal variability.

The formula used for the calculation is as follows:

$$Removal\ efficiency = (1 - \frac{C_e}{C_i}) * 100\%$$

Table I. Pollutant removal equations and rate constants for FWS constructed wetlands

Pollutant	Equation used	Rate constant	Rate constant units
BOD	(1)*	$K_T = 0.678(1.06)^{T-20}$	[d ⁻¹]
Fecal coliforms	(2)**	$K_1 = 0.3$	[m d ⁻¹]
Nitrogen			
<i>Nitrification</i>	(1)*	$K_T = 0.0389T$ $0 < T < 1^\circ C$ $K_T = 0.1367(1.15)^{T-10}$ $1 < T < 10^\circ C$ $K_T = 0.2187(1.048)^{T-20}$ $T > 10^\circ C$	[d ⁻¹] [d ⁻¹] [d ⁻¹]
<i>Denitrification</i>	(1)*	$K_T = 0.023T$ $0 < T < 1^\circ C$ $K_T = 1.15^{(T-20)}$ $T > 1^\circ C$	[d ⁻¹] [d ⁻¹]
Phosphorus	(2)**	$K_1 = 0.0273$	[m d ⁻¹]

*by Reed *et al.* (1995), **by Kadlec and Knight (1996).

The efficiency of a constructed wetland depends on soil acidity and wastewater quality. Soil acidity is widely recognized as affecting the availability and retention of heavy metals, complex compounds and nutrients. The optimal pH range for constructed wetlands is 6.5-8.5. Referring to the content of organic matter, its concentration should be sufficient to feed higher plants and bacterial communities, especially in the initial stages of constructed wetlands formation and during periods in the active growing seasons (Shchegolkova, 2018).

How can we use the constructed wetlands?

The constructed wetlands are part of a natural ecosystem and their effluent can be used in landscape management and forestry. For example, the fast-growing timber industry can best utilize the treated wastewater from the constructed wetlands (Anonymous, 2018).

Constructed wetlands are nowadays regarded as a part of the natural water cycle. If the treatment wetland is included in the water supply and sewage systems, then the use of water in an urban zone becomes much more efficient. Such a scheme can include short rotation forestry terrains and contribute to more economically and/or profitable water use.

Figure 4. Water supply and sewage systems in the treatment wetlands

Innovative "secondary" treatment for wastewater systems reduces the microbial load to acceptable limits, maximizing the release of useful substances (e.g. nitrogen and phosphorus), which can be used in agroforestry systems to provide nutrients and organic matter in the soil. According to this innovative approach a methodology was developed by the University of Basilicata, Italy, after testing was done on olive trees. From these previous pilot studies, it has emerged that properly controlled modifications of a conventional treatment plant, together with an accurate monitoring scheme which adjusts the provision of organic matter and nutrients to the irrigated soil, is a cost-effective system. It is one that maximizes the amount of "good" organic matter available for irrigation, while minimizing health risks (Monteverdi, 2014).

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